

TABLE I

S.No.	Compound	Colour	Elemental analysis Found (Calc.)			I.R. Spectra		pH for quantitative precipitation
			C%	H%	N%	C-N cm ⁻¹	C-S cm ⁻¹	
1.	(MDTC).K	White	29.31 (29.82)	3.80 (4.00)	6.95 (6.95)	1442	990	—
2.	(pipDTC).K	White	35.92 (36.14)	4.91 (5.05)	6.89 (7.02)	1445	990	—
3.	(pyDTC).K	White	32.39 (32.39)	4.30 (4.35)	7.48 (7.55)	1438	987	—
4.	(MDTC) ₄ Te	Yellow	30.95 (30.93)	4.13 (4.15)	7.08 (7.21)	1480	1000	3.5–6.5
5.	(pipDTC) ₄ Te	Yellow	37.30 (37.49)	5.19 (5.24)	7.05 (7.28)	1480	1000	3.5–6.0
6.	(pyDTC) ₄ Te	Redish Yellow	33.40 (33.79)	4.27 (4.52)	7.73 (7.86)	1470	995	3.5=6.0
7.	(MDTC) ₄ Se	Light Yellow	32.88 (33.00)	4.17 (4.43)	7.57 (7.69)	1480	980	3.0–5.0
8.	(pipDTC) ₄ Se	Yellow	40.0 (40.03)	5.67 (5.59)	7.48 (7.78)	1480	1000	3.0–5.0
9.	(pyDTC) ₄ Se	Yellow	36.99 (36.17)	4.52 (4.85)	8.51 (8.43)	1475	1000	3.0–5.0

absorptions⁶, whereas those containing monodentates R₂NC(S)S group show doublets for the two modes of vibrations⁷.

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Studies on the Complexes of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) with Benzamidothiosemicarbazide

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (NH₂CS NH NH₂) and its N-amino derivative (NH₂-NH-CS NH NH₂) thiocarbonylhydrazide, have long been known to possess biochemical and pharmacological¹ including

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anticarcinogenic², antibacterial and fungicidal³ properties. They have also been used in the industry⁴. Campbell and Grzeskowiak⁵ prepared two series of Cu(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazide and elucidated their structure employing ultraviolet and visible spectroscopic techniques. Ajayi *et al.*⁶ reported interaction of Pb(II) with NH₂C(X)NH NH₂ (X=O, S, Se) and calculated stability constant by polarographic method. Stability constant and heat of formation of Hg(II) complex of thiosemicarbazide were determined by Goddard and co-workers⁷.

In the present communication the results of our studies on the composition and structural characteristics of benzamidothiosemicarbazide (abbreviated as BTSC) and Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) have been reported.

Experimental

Benamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) was prepared by the method described by Verma⁸ and its solution prepared by dissolving weighed amounts in 80 : 20 ethyl alcohol : water mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solutions of copper acetate, mercuric chloride, and lead acetate were prepared by dissolving these salts (B. D. H. 'AR' grade) in doubly distilled air free water. The strengths of these solutions were determined by the usual methods.

Conductometric titrations of BTSC against Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) were carried out to determine the complexes. A series of solutions keeping the concentration constant and varying the metal (direct titration) and vice-versa (reverse titration) were prepared keeping the volume constant in each case. The plots of conduc-

tance versus concentration of metal (or ligand) give inflections corresponding to the metal-ligand interaction ratio. Phillips conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.62) was used for determining the conductance.

Amperometric titrations were carried on a manual polarograph in conjunction with a pye scalamp galvanometer. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out using $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ solution of the metal and the ligand in presence of $0.2 M$ KCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.008% gelatine as maximum suppressor. Purified nitrogen was bubbled through the solution for about five minutes after each addition of the titrant for deaeration of the solution. The titrations were carried out at -0.1 volts versus S.C.E. The observed diffusion current was corrected for change in volume during titration by multiplying with $(V+v)/(V)$ and plotted against the volume of the ligand or metal. The inflection points give the interaction ratio of the metal and ligand.

The isolation of these complexes was carried out as given below :—

250 ml of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ aqueous metal salt solution of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) was mixed with 500 ml of equimolecular solution of BTSC. The complexes which were white in colour precipitated, cooled and filtered, washed with water and recrystallised with hot methanol and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. The isolated complexes were analysed for metal and sulphur. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Analytical Results

Complex	% of metal		% of sulphur.	
	Found	Requires	Found	Requires
(BTSC) ₂ Cu	13.2033	13.1879	13.2994	13.2918
(BTSC) ₂ Hg	32.4218	32.4269	10.3460	10.3494
(BTSC) ₂ Pb	33.1034	33.0120	10.2731	10.2400

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with the help of Gouy's magnetic balance, having a semimicrometer balance, model C Meltlov Zoric type H₁₆ No. 140050 at 31° . The observed molar susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetic contributions. The Cu(II) complex showed a magnetic moment of 1.96 B.M. (corrected molar susceptibility $X_M \times 10^{-6} = 1570$ c.g.s. units).

The i.r. spectra of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes of BTSC were taken in KBr medium by the method of fast scanning using 'Beckman I.R. 20'.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies show that aqueous solutions of cupric acetate when mixed with a solution of BTSC (prepared in $80 : 20$ ethyl alcohol-water mixture) gave a blue black coloured solution which on standing yielded a whitish grey precipitate. In the case of mercuric chloride and lead acetate, rapid precipitation of a white crystalline complex was observed. Investigations on Cu(I) and Hg(I) with BTSC show no interactions. These complexes were characterised by different physico-chemical techniques.

In all the cases sharp breaks were observed for both direct and reverse conductometric titrations. For all the three metals (Cu(II), Hg(II), and Pb(II)) breaks corresponding to $1:2$ metal-ligand ratio were obtained.

BTSC gave oxidation currents and the plateau was found to exist at -0.1 volts. Therefore, a constant potential of -0.1 volts was applied for all the amperometric titrations. Normal curves were obtained and gave sharp breaks confirming the stoichiometric results of conductometric studies.

Results of chemical analysis (Table 1) further supported the stoichiometric ratios obtained from electrometric studies.

The Cu(II) complex of composition $\text{Cu}(\text{BTSC})_2$ exhibited magnetic moment of 1.96 B. M. which suggested square planar stereochemistry involving sp^2d hybridization.

Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes of BTSC have $3d^{10}$ configuration and were found to be diamagnetic and possibly had tetrahedral stereochemistry.

The infrared absorption band at 3280 cm^{-1} observed in the infrared spectrum of BTSC was due to NH and NH_2 stretching vibrations. In the Cu(II), and Hg(II) complexes, this band was shifted to higher frequencies 3400 cm^{-1} and 3320 cm^{-1} while in Pb(II) complex this band was broadened in the region $3440 - 3480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that the NH_2 group of hydrazine was not involved in the complex formation⁹.

The absorption bands, occurring at 1318 cm^{-1} , 790 cm^{-1} and 760 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching. Similar assignments have been made for thio acetamide and other thio compounds^{10,11}. In the metal complexes, these bands showed a shift to lower wave lengths, the lowering being primarily due to the binding of sulphur to the metal¹². These bands appear at 1298 cm^{-1} , 745 cm^{-1} , 720 cm^{-1} , for the Cu(II) complex, at 1300 cm^{-1} , 775 cm^{-1} , 735 cm^{-1} , for Hg(II) and at 1310 cm^{-1} , 765 cm^{-1} , 735 cm^{-1} for Pb(II).

The absorption band at 1630 cm^{-1} occurring in ligand spectrum was due to the bending vibrations of the amino and the amide groups. The appearance of the amide band at the same frequency (1630 cm^{-1}) instead of a decrease indicated the non participation

of the amido nitrogen atom. However, disappearance and lowering of NCS bend frequencies occurring at 1180 cm^{-1} and 1140 cm^{-1} to 1110 cm^{-1} in Cu(II), and at 1160 cm^{-1} and 1110 cm^{-1} in the case of Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes, indicated the participation of nitrogen atom (attached to amido nitrogen) in bond formation.

The new bands appearing at 460 cm^{-1} , 398 cm^{-1} and at 480 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes respectively were attributed to M-N (metal-nitrogen) stretching frequencies. Further two bands appearing at 330 cm^{-1} and 296 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Hg-complex and at 340 cm^{-1} and 310 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Pb(II) complex were assignable to Hg-S and Pb-S stretching frequencies respectively. However, in case of Cu(II) complex very weak M-S absorption bands were observed in the spectrum of copper complex and, therefore, its exact assignment became difficult. The following structure was assigned to these complexes

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Schiff Bases as Chelating Agents for Nickel (II)

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TWO types of ligands were prepared and identified as reported earlier¹⁻³. Their general structural formulae are as follows :

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Isolation of Nickel (II) complexes :

On mixing ethanolic solutions of nickel chloride hexahydrate (A.R.) and the corresponding ligands in stoichiometric ratio (1:2) different coloured solutions resulted in separate experiments. The reaction mixture was evaporated nearly on water bath ; methanol (10 ml) was added to it and was left at room temperature for slow evaporation. The coloured crystalline compounds separated out ; which were filtered off, washed with ethanol and then dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

General Structures of Schiff Bases :

where,

R=4-Acenaphthyl,

4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumaryl,

4-methylphenyl.

R'=2-Carboxylicphenyl, 2-hydroxyphenyl.

Physico - Chemical Measurements and Instruments Used :

The electronic diffuse reflectance spectra were taken in a Ziess PMQ II spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment RA₈. Electronic spectra in specpure solvents were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell. Magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance and I. R. spectral studies of the compounds have been made as reported earlier¹⁻³. Elemental analysis of the compounds was made at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Acidic complexes in aqueous and DMSO medium show comparable molar conductance values.

Results and Discussions

All the complexes are soluble in DMF, DMSO, NM and benzene. The molar conductance (λ_M) values indicate their electrolytic as well as nonelectrolytic nature⁴.

The room temperature magnetic moments of all the complexes (Table 1) fall within the range 2.83-3.45 B. M. expected for octahedral spin free Ni(II) complexes⁵.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the present Ni(II) complexes are characterised by three main bands as shown in Table 2 which are in close agreement to those predicted from Ballhausen and Liehr⁶ energy level diagram for Ni(II) ions in O_h symmetry. The results are more or less in good agreement with those reported